

The Ibero-American Indicators of Sport and Physical Activity for Sustainable Development

Report on Results and
Lessons Learned From
the First Phase of the
Indicator Pilot

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Introduction

By mandate of the High Authorities of Sport in Ibero-America, including Ministers, the Ibero-American Sports Council (CID), UNESCO, and the German Agency for International Cooperation (GIZ), have developed the first common indicators to measure the impact of sport and physical activity on sustainable development in Ibero-America. More recently, the Development Bank of Latin America and the Caribbean (CAF) and the Research Centre in Sports Science of the King Juan Carlos University have also joined the Consortium.

The purpose of these indicators is to provide countries with periodic, standardized, and comparable information on the impact of sport in various dimensions of sustainable development, as well as to enable the periodic evaluation of policies to identify opportunities for improvement and substantiate achievements and results. Additionally, they aim to facilitate the measurement of the social return on sport, promoting increased investment in sport and physical activity.

During the XXIX General Assembly of the CID, held in Cartagena, Colombia, in May 2023, the creation of twelve indicators and four key data points for implementation in the region was unanimously approved. Additionally, a pilot implementation in a group of applicant countries was approved, conducted between August 2023 and March 2024. The countries that participated in the first stage of the pilot were Chile, Costa Rica, and Ecuador.

The objective of the pilot was to validate the relevance and applicability of these indicators for scaling them across the entire region, as well as to conduct an initial calculation based on the availability of information sources. Based on this, a country-specific report was generated on their situation, along with another report on cross-cutting results and lessons learned.

This document corresponds to the Report on Results and Lessons Learned from the pilot implementation. It describes the value of the indicators and key data points that were successfully calculated during the pilot, the technical assessment of the indicators by the participating countries, and a set of findings, lessons learned, and recommendations for the next phases of the pilot.

The report is complemented by the Country Report for each participating country in the pilot, as well as by the specific technical sheets for the calculation of its indicators. The country reports detail the specific context and challenges each country faced in calculating the indicators, while the technical sheets outline the technical procedure for their calculation.

I. Ibero-American Indicators of Sport and Physical Activity for Development

The approved indicators and key data points for implementation in the Ibero-American region are described in Table 1. As can be observed, the indicators are classified according to their area of impact or the related sustainable development theme.

Table 1. Key data points and Indicators of the Impact of Sport and Physical Activity on Sustainable Development

Key data points	
1. There is a recent national survey on sports practice and physical activity, stratified by gender and age.	
2. Governmental rank of the national authority for sports and physical activity	
3. Physical education is an independent mandatory subject in primary and secondary education at the national level.	
4. There are legal frameworks to promote, enforce, and oversee gender equality and non-discrimination in sports and physical activity.	
Indicators*	Area of Impact
1. Percentage of the national public budget invested in sports and physical activity	Economy
2. Percentage of the contribution of sports and physical activity to the national GDP	
3. Percentage of the population sufficiently physically active stratified by gender and age	Health
4. Percentage of deaths related to physical inactivity	
5. Percentage of schools providing the minimum number of minutes of physical education	Education
6. Percentage of school students sufficiently physically active stratified by gender	
7. Percentage of the national sport entity's budget focused on gender programs	Gender equality
8. Percentage of women in managerial positions within the national sports entity	
9. Percentage of the gender gap among the sufficiently physically active population	
10. Percentage of the national sport entity's budget focused on programs for people with disabilities	Inclusion of people with disabilities
11. Percentage of the disability gap among the sufficiently physically active population	
12. Percentage of government programs using sport as an instrument for peace and coexistence	Peace and social cohesion

Note: * The indicators may have slight differences in name for each country due to the terminology and methodology used by each. The precise wording of the indicators for each country should be consulted in its Country Report and technical data sheet document.

It is important to note that each indicator is accompanied by a technical sheet that provides a detailed explanation to ensure its correct interpretation and implementation. These sheets include key information fields such as definition, justification, calculation method, unit of measurement, year, frequency, geographical coverage, data sources, and relevant concepts, among others.

The wording of the indicators presented in Table 1 already incorporates the recommendations and contributions from the countries that participated in the pilot. However, it is likely that further modifications will be made as the different stages of the pilot progress.

II. Process of Creating Indicators

The process of creating indicators, from the mandate of the XXVIII CID Assembly in the Dominican Republic for their creation to the presentation of the pilot results at the XXX Assembly in Washington, spans a two-year period of intensive work between the countries in the region and the institutions that make up the Consortium responsible for their implementation.

The timeline of the indicator creation process is shown in Figure 1, highlighting the main political, technical, and operational milestones that led to the presentation of the pilot results.

Figure 1. *Timeline of the Indicator Creation Process*

An important aspect to highlight is that the current set of 12 indicators and four key data points is the result of a broader set of 60 indicators that was used as the subject of discussion in an extensive participatory analysis process in the region. This process included the application of an online exploratory questionnaire with the participation of 83 specialists from various fields; 18 semi-structured interviews with experts from academia and representatives from governments and international organizations; two focus groups with 22 government representatives; and a virtual preliminary validation meeting in November 2022. This event involved 37 government representatives from 17 countries in the region. Additionally, a technical validation was carried out by the governments of the region during the seminar: "Plan for the Creation of Sport Indicators for Sustainable Development in Ibero-America," held in Santa Cruz de la Sierra, Bolivia, in March 2023.

As a result of this process, the implementation of 12 indicators and four key data points was approved at the XXIX General Assembly of the CID in Cartagena, Colombia, to then begin the pilot implementation in September 2023 and conclude in March 2024.

III. Results of the Indicator Implementation

Regarding the results of the indicator implementation, that is, the extent to which it was possible to calculate the values of the key data points and indicators, the following results are available (see details in Table 2):

- Of the four key data points, all four were implemented by the three countries (100% implementation).
- Chile, of the 12 indicators, was able to implement eight (66.6% implementation).
- Costa Rica, of the 12 indicators, was able to implement four (33.3% implementation).
- Ecuador, of the 12 indicators, was able to implement seven (58.3% implementation).

Table 2. Results of the Implementation of Key data points and Indicators in the Pilot

Name of the data point or indicator	Value of the data point or indicator		
	Chile	Costa Rica	Ecuador
Key data points	Value		
1. There is a recent national survey on sports practice and physical activity, stratified by gender and age.	Partially	Partially	Partially
2. Governmental rank of the national authority for sports and physical activity	Ministry	Autonomous Organ	Ministry
3. Physical education is an independent mandatory subject in primary and secondary education at the national level.	Partially	Partially	Partially
4. There are legal frameworks to promote, enforce, and oversee gender equality and non-discrimination in sports and physical activity.	Yes	Yes	Partially
Indicators	Value		
1. Percentage of the national public budget invested in sports and physical activity	0.62%	No value	0.23%
2. Percentage of the contribution of sports and physical activity to the national GDP	No value	No value	No value
3. Percentage of the population sufficiently physically active stratified by gender and age*	18.7%	63.9%	78.3%
4. Percentage of deaths related to physical inactivity	8.3%	11.4%	11.0%
5. Percentage of schools providing the minimum number of minutes of physical education	No value	No value	No value
6. Percentage of school students sufficiently physically active stratified by gender	16.5%	No value	No value
7. Percentage of the national sport entity's budget focused on gender programs	0%	No value	No value
8. Percentage of women in managerial positions within the national sports entity	52.4%	36.4%	48.6%
9. Percentage of the gender gap among the sufficiently physically active population	42.9%	15.3%	17.0%
10. Percentage of the national sport entity's budget focused on programs for people with disabilities	No value	No value	3.3%
11. Percentage of the disability gap among the sufficiently physically active population	No value	No value	No value
12. Percentage of government programs using sport as an instrument for peace and coexistence**	4.3%	No value	1.3%

Note: * Chile uses a stricter methodology for estimating its percentage; therefore, it is not strictly comparable with the percentages of Costa Rica and Ecuador.

** The indicator is not strictly comparable between countries because Chile considers the total of "social and non-social programs in the health, sports, and life dimension" as the scope, while Ecuador considers all "projects from the Social Development, Health, and Human Talent cabinets."

Although it was not possible to implement all the indicators, the results from the first stage of the pilot are considered positive, as they exceeded the initial expectations based on the available information and provided important lessons for the subsequent phases of the pilot.

The analysis of the factors explaining the results in the countries is described across the following sections of this document and specifically in each of the Country Reports. However, in general, these factors are primarily related to the limited availability of primary data sources, such as: nationally representative surveys, census administrative records, and a satellite account for sport and physical activity. Additionally, they are also linked to the limited technical and operational capacity of the countries to carry out the pilot within the established timeframe.

It is important to note that for some indicators, there are small methodological differences due to discrepancies in the terminology and administrative structures of the countries. However, except for two cases, for the majority of indicators, such differences are minor and are fully identified in the technical sheet for each country.

The technical sheets for the indicators provide a detailed description of the main characteristics or technical attributes of the indicators and facilitate their correct interpretation, implementation, and scalability. The technical sheets are essential for replicating the calculation of the indicators, understanding their scope, encouraging discussions among experts, and promoting information transparency.

The key fields of information included in the technical sheets are: indicator definition, justification, calculation method, unit of measurement, year, frequency, geographical coverage, data sources, and concepts used, among others.

The first indicator with significant differences between countries is Indicator 3: "Percentage of the population sufficiently physically active stratified by gender and age". This is because Chile presents a considerable difference in its percentage compared to Costa Rica and Ecuador, which can partly be explained by the demographic profile of its population, but also by differences in the questionnaire used compared to those of the other countries. However, since it was not possible to access the specific questionnaires from Costa Rica and Ecuador (Chile did provide theirs), nor the microdata resulting from the information gathering (no country made the microdata directly available to the public), it is impossible to know for sure.

The second indicator with significant differences is Indicator 12: "Percentage of government programs using sport as an instrument for peace and coexistence". This is mainly due to the different categories and accounting systems of the countries. For example, Chile uses the term "programs," while Ecuador refers to "projects." Additionally, Chile groups the programs into different government categories compared to Ecuador, which could significantly affect the reported percentages.

IV. Technical Assessment of the Indicators

The technical assessment of the indicators involved evaluating certain attributes of the key data points and indicators by the technical team of the countries. The attributes assessed were:

- *Clarity*: An indicator is clear when there is no doubt about what it aims to measure. In other words, the name of the indicator is self-explanatory and aligns with the calculation method, which is clearly specified.
- *Feasibility*: An indicator is feasible when the calculation method and information sources are such that the indicator can be estimated with the available human, financial, material, and informational resources. If these resources are lacking, the effort required to achieve the indicator does not entail an extraordinary effort.
- *Relevance*: An indicator is relevant when it provides effective information about a higher-level theme linked to the objectives of policies related to sport, physical activity, or physical education.
- *Cost-effectiveness*: An indicator is cost-effective if the benefit of generating the information for its calculation outweighs the economic cost required to calculate it.

For the above, the countries answered a series of questions associated with each attribute through an online document. For each question, there were three response options: yes, no, and partially.

Table 3 presents the general summary of the assessment of the key data points and indicators. The questions related to each attribute and the breakdown of responses by country and indicator can be found in the annex of this document. To facilitate the interpretation of the results, the responses of "Yes" were assigned a value of two, "Partially" a value of one, and "No" a value of zero.

It is important to note that the results of the assessments and recommendations from the countries were mostly incorporated into the wording and calculation methods of the key data points and indicators presented in this report. In other words, the indicators already reflect the improvements identified during the assessment process, or in cases where doubts arose, they were clarified at the time.

Regarding the general results, the feasibility attribute was the lowest of the four used (1.5 on a scale of 0 to 2), which is mainly explained by the lack of information sources or the effort required to obtain them. In contrast, the best-evaluated attribute was economy, with an average of 2 for the key data points and 1.8 for the indicators.

Table 3. *Technical Assessment of the Countries on the Key data points and Indicators at the Start of the Pilot* (The maximum average value is 2, and the minimum is 0)*

Key data points	C	F	R	CE	AVG
1. There is a recent national survey on sports practice and physical activity, stratified by gender and age.	1.8	1.4	1.5	2.0	1.7
2. Governmental rank of the national authority for sports and physical activity	2.0	1.7	1.7	2.0	1.8
3. Physical education is an independent mandatory subject in primary and secondary education at the national level.	1.7	1.6	2.0	2.0	1.8
4. There are legal frameworks to promote, enforce, and oversee gender equality and non-discrimination in sports and physical activity.	1.4	1.4	2.0	2.0	1.7
Average value for the key data points	1.7	1.5	1.8	2.0	
Indicators	C	F	R	CE	AVG
1. Percentage of the national public budget invested in sports and physical activity	1.9	1.5	1.7	1.7	1.7
2. Percentage of the contribution of sports and physical activity to the national GDP	1.9	1.0	1.7	1.7	1.6
3. Percentage of the population sufficiently physically active stratified by gender and age	1.7	1.4	1.8	2.0	1.7
4. Percentage of deaths related to physical inactivity	1.1	1.3	1.5	1.7	1.4
5. Percentage of schools providing the minimum number of minutes of physical education	2.0	1.3	2	2	1.8
6. Percentage of school students sufficiently physically active stratified by gender	1.8	1.4	2	2	1.8
7. Percentage of the national sport entity's budget focused on gender programs	1.9	1.6	2	2	1.9
8. Percentage of women in managerial positions within the national sports entity	1.9	1.8	1.7	2	1.8
9. Percentage of the gender gap among the sufficiently physically active population	2.0	1.7	2	2	1.9
10. Percentage of the national sport entity's budget focused on programs for people with disabilities	1.9	1.7	2	2	1.9
11. Percentage of the disability gap among the sufficiently physically active population	2.0	1.4	2	2	1.8
12. Percentage of government programs using sport as an instrument for peace and coexistence	1.9	1.7	1.8	2	1.8
Average value for the indicator	1.8	1.5	1.8	1.9	

Note: C = Clarity; F = Feasibility; R = Relevance; CE = Cost-effectiveness; AVG = Average; * Most of the observations or recommendations identified have already been incorporated into the wording of the indicators presented in this document, as well as the calculation methods for the indicators described in their technical data sheets.

Specifically for the indicators, the one with the lowest average rating was Indicator 4, which is mainly explained by the technical complexity of its calculation. However, it is an indicator generated by an external source for the countries, meaning the countries do not need to calculate it themselves.

Since most of the average ratings were in the range of 1.7 to 2 (on a scale from 0 to 2), and the lowest detected was 1.4, it is considered that, in general, the indicators are understandable and appropriate for implementation. It is important to note that this evaluation was conducted at the start of the pilot, so it is highly likely that, upon conducting a new analysis, the assessment ratings will be higher.

V. Findings on the Operational Processes for Generating Indicators

The operational processes refer to the flow of information and working mechanisms for generating the indicators, as well as the responsibilities of the actors involved in generating, validating, and using the information. Despite the strong political commitment of the countries participating in the pilot, as well as the significant involvement of their technical teams, important findings and areas of opportunity related to the operational processes were documented during the pilot execution. Below are the most significant of these findings:

- a) *Wide Variability in Operational Processes Between Countries:* Despite the countries sharing many institutional similarities, significant differences are observed in the administrative and governmental accounting categories related to the generation of indicators. This leads to challenges in ensuring full comparability of the indicators across the region.
- b) *Limited Documentation of Operational Processes for Generating Indicators:* Generally, there is limited documentation regarding the traceability of the processes for generating the information required for the indicators, as well as the actors responsible for it. This situation complicates the identification of the pathways to produce information and the sharing and management of knowledge.
- c) *Limited Reliable, Systematized, and Updated Information Sources:* Partly related to the lack of documentation on operational processes, but also due to the lack of financial and human resources and training, there are insufficient information sources to generate all the indicators.
- d) *Survey Methodological Documents with Limited Public Access:* The methodological documents for surveys are not fully publicly available, making it impossible to establish with complete certainty whether the questionnaires used to collect the data are truly comparable across countries. Additionally, no country provides the public with easy and direct access to the microdata from the surveys, which significantly hinders external validation and use by experts for conducting related statistical analysis.
- e) *Opportunities for Improving Institutional Coordination to Generate Information:* There was a certain level of fragmentation in the availability of information within countries, meaning that it is necessary to improve coordination between different sectors to ensure that the collected information is complete and systematic.
- f) *Insufficient Specialized Technical Staff in Indicators, Monitoring, and Evaluation:* One of the most significant obstacles to advancing adequately in the pilot's implementation was the insufficient number of technical staff in the countries to meet the established time commitments for conducting the pilot.
- g) *Important to Capitalize on the Political Commitment of Countries in Better Operational Processes for Generating Indicators:* The high political commitment of the countries to conduct the pilot should be translated into better operational conditions for the indicators.

VI. Lessons Learned and Recommendations

Lessons Learned refer to general situations observed during the pilot that involve insights and recommendations aimed at improving the implementation of the indicators in subsequent phases of the pilot, as well as ensuring their general implementation and long-term sustainability.

In Table 4, the most important lessons and recommendations identified during the pilot are presented. Most of the recommendations are directed at the countries, but some are also addressed to the Consortium and its technical team.

Table 4. *Lessons Learned and Recommendations*

Lessons Learned	Recommendations
It is crucial to have more technical staff in the countries: delegates appointed by high authorities did not have exclusive dedication to the pilot project as was initially agreed.	Ensure that the technical teams in the countries have sufficient time availability for the pilot: especially to work online, complete required instruments, gather information, and participate in meetings.
Expand and improve the training of the technical teams in the countries: in some cases, significant technical limitations were observed in understanding and operationalizing the indicators.	Provide intensive training before and during the pilot: conduct multiple training sessions on the technical sheets of the indicators as well as on the formats and tools for online data collection.
Need to involve academia: it is important to build synergy with other sectors to enhance information generation and produce better-documented analyses.	Partnership with a local university for indicator development: collaborating with a local university, which has contextual knowledge and time availability, would be highly beneficial in strengthening the technical capacities and operational response of the countries.
Different challenges and solutions for each country: each country faced unique challenges and developed different solutions that could be valuable for other countries to learn from.	Share experiences and knowledge among countries: emphasizing the importance of linking national initiatives with international standards, ensuring the alignment of national policies with best practices
Improve the Consortium's administrative framework: it is necessary to formalize the Consortium's establishment to streamline administrative processes for the implementation of the indicators.	Formalize long-term strategic partnerships: establishing medium- and long-term agreements between the institutions participating in the Consortium and between the Consortium and the countries would strengthen the administrative and financial certainty of the indicator implementation.
Opportunities for improvement in the pilot methodology: throughout the pilot, relevant contributions emerged to enhance the methodology and operational instruments.	Strengthening the participatory approach of the methodologies: it is essential to expand the participatory process involving countries and experts from academia to strengthen the working methodologies and operational implementation instruments.
Without sufficient investment, it will not be possible to calculate certain indicators: without new representative surveys, censuses, or complete administrative records, calculating some indicators will not be feasible.	Need for funding for certain indicators: seek partnerships with international financial institutions focused on financing the development of monitoring and evaluation capacities regarding the impact of sport on sustainable development.

VII. Financing to Generate Information and Develop Indicators

As already stated, one of the most important limitations for generating indicators is the lack of sufficient budget in the governments of the region to finance the creation of the necessary sources of information for calculating the indicators.

This section identifies those areas with the greatest need for government financing to implement the indicators.

The first area of financing concerns the primary sources of information for the indicators (see Table 5), and the second the institutional and operational environment for generating the indicators, specifically: capacity building, generation of studies and publications, and international cooperation schemes and exchange of experiences.

In Table 5, key data points with values below the required level and indicators for which calculation was not possible, primarily due to the lack of an information source that requires significant financing, are described. The last column provides a brief explanation of the justification and the specific purpose of the financing.

Table 5. *Indicators with Total or Partial Absence of Information Sources Subject to Financing*

Key Data Point or Indicator	Funding opportunity	Country	Explication
D.1. There is a recent national survey on sports practice and physical activity, stratified by gender and age.	Justification	Chile, Costa Rica and Ecuador	The data has partial compliance value due to the fact that the surveys are over 5 years old and lack sufficient disaggregation by age and sex or gender.
	Country roadmap		Forming an interinstitutional team to identify the technical and financial requirements for obtaining more disaggregated and regular surveys is necessary.
	Funding objective		National representative surveys should be conducted for individuals under 18 years old, between 18 and 64 years old, and over 65 years old, disaggregated by sex or gender, with microdata made publicly available.
I.2. Percentage of the contribution of sports and physical activity to the national GDP	Justification	Chile, Costa Rica and Ecuador	The indicator has no value due to the absence of a satellite account for sport and physical activity, or a national accounting system that allows for a precise, reliable, and disaggregated estimation of the sector's contribution to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP).
	Country roadmap		Forming an interinstitutional team to identify the technical and financial requirements for designing a satellite account is essential.
	Funding objective		The creation of a satellite account for sport and physical activity is necessary, as its implementation typically involves considerable financial and technical challenges for the national governing entities of sport and physical activity in the region.

I.5. Percentage of schools providing the minimum number of minutes of physical education	Justification	Chile, Costa Rica and Ecuador	The indicator has no value due to the lack of an administrative census or a representative survey that allows for the calculation of the indicator.
	Country roadmap		It is essential to establish the necessary mechanisms to conduct an administrative census or a national representative survey.
	Funding objective		An administrative census or a national representative survey should be carried out to enable accurate data collection for the indicator.
I.11. Percentage of the disability gap among the sufficiently physically active population	Justification	Chile, Costa Rica and Ecuador	The indicator has no value due to the absence of a representative survey on sport and physical activity for people with disabilities.
	Country roadmap		It is necessary to integrate an interdisciplinary working group to define the concepts and measurements to be included in the representative survey.
	Funding objective		A representative survey on sport and physical activity for people with disabilities should be conducted, disaggregated by age and sex or gender, and with data no older than five years.

Regarding the areas of financing for the institutional and operational environment to generate the indicators, the following are highlighted:

- *Capacity Building:* There is a need to expand and improve the training of technical teams on aspects of measurement and design of evaluation and monitoring indicators. Trainings require basic concepts of causality, impact measurement, and design of representative probabilistic surveys, as well as their application in the field of sport and physical activity.
- *Studies and Publications:* To create a positive and conducive environment for investment in sport and physical activity, it is necessary to publicize the enormous impact of sport on sustainable development and its status as a dimension of development. For this, it is crucial to disseminate achievements, progress, and challenges through public policy documents or academic studies, for which financing is required for their creation and dissemination.
- *International Cooperation:* As documented in the pilot, from their own perspective and context, countries can produce creative solutions to certain challenges or problems that should be shared with other countries. Similarly, various dimensions of measuring sport and physical activity are still in relevant conceptual discussions, which requires constant interaction and debate between government specialists and academia to reach some consensus. Therefore, it is essential to have sufficient funds to finance international cooperation events and exchanges of experiences among specialists and decision-makers.

Conclusions

The objective of the pilot was successfully achieved by implementing all four key data points and, on average, more than half of the indicators. Additionally, the technical attributes of the indicators were validated by the countries, and significant operational and administrative challenges were identified that, together, will help improve the implementation of the pilot in its next phases and, eventually, for its execution across the region.

The main challenges in implementing the indicators lie in improving the technical capacities of countries to generate information, documenting operational processes, and institutionalizing common practices for measurement and monitoring. Additionally, there is the challenge of increasing public investment to have more comprehensive and continuous representative surveys, and even a satellite account for sport and physical activity. This highlights the importance to establish partnerships with academia or international financing institutions.

The pilot's results have fulfilled the purpose of providing information to improve the conditions in the region for obtaining periodic, standardized, and comparable data on the impact of sport on development and measuring its social return. From this, the importance of sport as a dimension of development has been highlighted, and it may better support the achievements and results of policies in the region.

Annex. Technical Evaluation Details of the Indicators

Table 1A. Detailed assessment of countries regarding the clarity of key data points at the start of the pilot* (The maximum average value is 2 and the minimum is 0)

Question	Country	Value for each key data point				
		1	2	3	4	AVG
Is the data point name self-explanatory (correctly expresses the unit of measurement, does not use acronyms or defines them precisely)?	CHL	2	2	2	2	2.0
	CRI	2	2	2	2	2.0
	ECU	1	2	2	2	1.7
Is the data point calculation method consistent with its name?	CHL	2	2	1	1	1.5
	CRI	2	2	2	0	1.5
	ECU	2	2	2	2	2.0
Are the data point validation criteria clear and self-explanatory?	CHL	1	2	1	2	1.5
	CRI	2	2	2	2	2.0
	ECU	2	2	2	2	2.0
Is the data point calculation method consistent with the validation criteria?	CHL	2	2	1	0	1.2
	CRI	2	2	2	0	1.5
	ECU	2	2	2	2	2.0
Average for each key data point		1.8	2.0	1.7	1.4	

Note: * Most of the observations or recommendations identified have already been incorporated into the wording of the indicators presented in this document, as well as the calculation methods for the indicators described in their technical sheets.

Table 2A. Detailed assessment of countries regarding the feasibility of key data points at the start of the pilot* (The maximum average value is 2 and the minimum is 0)

Question	Country	Value for each key data point				
		1	2	3	4	AVG
Is the data point measurement frequency consistent with the update of the information sources?	CHL	2	2	2	2	2.0
	CRI	1	2	2	2	1.7
	ECU	0	2	2	2	1.5
Are the validation criteria considered, or can they be assessed based on the information sources?	CHL	2	2	2	2	2.0
	CRI	2	2	2	1	1.7
	ECU	2	2	2	2	2.0
Are the information sources currently available to calculate the data point from the national sports body or official government sources?	CHL	2	2	2	2	2.0
	CRI	2	2	2	1	1.7
	ECU	2	2	0	2	1.5
If the information sources to calculate the data point are not currently available from the national sports body or official government sources, would it be possible to generate them without requiring extraordinary human or material resources from the government?	CHL	0	0	2	1	0.7
	CRI	0	0	0	0	0
	ECU	2	2	1	0	1.2
Average for each key data point		1.4	1.7	1.6	1.4	

Note: * Most of the observations or recommendations identified have already been incorporated into the wording of the indicators presented in this document, as well as the calculation methods for the indicators described in their technical sheets.

Table 3A. Detailed assessment of countries regarding the relevance of key data points at the start of the pilot* (The maximum average value is 2 and the minimum is 0)

Question	Country	Value for each key data point				
		1	2	3	4	AVG
Is the data point related to a higher-level theme linked to policy or program objectives for sport, physical activity, or physical education?	CHL	2	2	2	2	2.0
	CRI	1	2	2	2	1.7
	ECU	2	2	2	2	2.0
Does the data point effectively provide information on an outcome achieved by policies or programs for sport, physical activity, or physical education?	CHL	1	2	2	2	1.7
	CRI	2	0	2	2	1.5
	ECU	1	2	2	2	1.7
Average for each key data point		1.5	1.7	2	2	

Note: * Most of the observations or recommendations identified have already been incorporated into the wording of the indicators presented in this document, as well as the calculation methods for the indicators described in their technical sheets.

Table 4A. Detailed assessment of countries regarding the cost-effectiveness of key data points at the start of the pilot* (The maximum average value is 2 and the minimum is 0)

Question	Country	Value for each key data point				
		1	2	3	4	AVG
Does the utility of the data point for measuring the contribution of sport, physical education, or physical activity to the achievement of a sustainable development goal justify the cost or effort associated with its calculation?	CHL	2	2	2	2	2.0
	CRI	2	2	2	2	2.0
	ECU	2	2	2	2	2.0
Average for each key data point		2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	

Note: * Most of the observations or recommendations identified have already been incorporated into the wording of the indicators presented in this document, as well as the calculation methods for the indicators described in their technical sheets.

Table 5A. Detailed assessment of countries regarding the clarity of the indicators at the start of the pilot* (The maximum average value is 2 and the minimum is 0)

Question	Country	Value for each indicator												AVG
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	
Is the indicator name self-explanatory (correctly expresses the unit of measurement, does not use acronyms or defines them precisely)?	CHL	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	1.8
	CRI	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1.9
	ECU	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	1	2	1	1.7
Is the calculation formula for the indicator consistent with its name?	CHL	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1.9
	CRI	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1.9
	ECU	2	2	2	0	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1.8
Is the definition of the indicator consistent with its name?	CHL	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1.9
	CRI	2	2	1	1	2	0	2	2	2	2	2	2	1.7
	ECU	2	2	2	0	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1.8
Is the definition of the indicator consistent with its calculation formula?	CHL	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1.8
	CRI	2	2	2	1	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	1.8
	ECU	2	2	2	0	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1.8
Are the units of measurement for the variables in the calculation formula of the indicator consistent?	CHL	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2.0
	CRI	2	2	2	1	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	1.8
	ECU	2	2	2	0	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1.8
Does the description of the variables in the calculation formula of the indicator allow for understanding all the elements or concepts it includes?	CHL	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1.9
	CRI	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1.9
	ECU	2	0	2	1	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	1	1.6
Average for each indicator		1.9	1.9	1.7	1.1	2.0	1.8	1.9	1.9	2.0	1.9	2.0	1.9	

Note: * Most of the observations or recommendations identified have already been incorporated into the wording of the indicators presented in this document, as well as the calculation methods for the indicators described in their technical sheets.

Table 6A. Detailed assessment of countries regarding the feasibility of the indicators at the start of the pilot* (The maximum average value is 2 and the minimum is 0)

Question	Country	Value for each indicator												
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	AVG
Is the measurement frequency of all the variables that make up the indicator consistent with the update of the information sources?	CHL	2	2	1	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1.8
	CRI	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1.9
	ECU	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
Are the variables used in the calculation method of the indicator considered in the information sources?	CHL	2	1	2	2	0	2	1	2	2	0	2	2	1.5
	CRI	2	2	2	0	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1.8
	ECU	2	0	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1.8
Are the information sources currently available to calculate the indicator from the national sports body or official government sources?	CHL	1	0	2	0	2	1	2	2	2	1	2	2	1.7
	CRI	2	0	1	1	2	1	2	2	2	2	0	0	1.2
	ECU	1	1	1	2	0	1	1	2	2	1	0	2	1.2
If the information sources to calculate the indicator are not currently available, would it be possible to generate them without requiring extraordinary human or material resources from the government?	CHL	0	1	0	2	2	0	0	0	1	2	2	2	1
	CRI	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	2	0	2	0	1	0.6
	ECU	2	1	2	2	1	1	1	2	2	2	1	2	1.6
Average for each indicator		1.5	1.0	1.4	1.3	1.3	1.4	1.6	1.8	1.7	1.7	1.4	1.7	

Note: * Most of the observations or recommendations identified have already been incorporated into the wording of the indicators presented in this document, as well as the calculation methods for the indicators described in their technical sheets.

Table 7A. Detailed assessment of countries regarding the relevance of the indicators at the start of the pilot* (The maximum average value is 2 and the minimum is 0)

Question	Country	Value for each indicator												AVG
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	
Does the indicator address a higher-level theme linked to policy or program objectives for sport, physical activity, or physical education?	CHL	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1.9
	CRI	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2.0
	ECU	1	2	2	1	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	1.7
Does the indicator effectively provide information on an outcome achieved by policies or programs for sport, physical activity, or physical education?	CHL	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2.0
	CRI	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2.0
	ECU	1	0	1	0	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	1.4
Average for each indicator		1.7	1.7	1.8	1.5	2	2	2	1.7	2	2	2	1.8	

Note: * Most of the observations or recommendations identified have already been incorporated into the wording of the indicators presented in this document, as well as the calculation methods for the indicators described in their technical sheets.

Table 8A. Detailed assessment of countries regarding the cost-effectiveness of the indicators at the start of the pilot* (The maximum average value is 2 and the minimum is 0)

Question	Country	Value for each indicator												AVG
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	
Does the utility of the indicator for measuring the contribution of sport, physical education, or physical activity to the achievement of a sustainable development goal justify the cost or effort associated with its calculation?	CHL	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1.9
	CRI	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
	ECU	1	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1.8
Average for each indicator		1.7	1.7	2	1.7	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	

Note: * Most of the observations or recommendations identified have already been incorporated into the wording of the indicators presented in this document, as well as the calculation methods for the indicators described in their technical sheets.